

ELDER ACTIVE CITIZENS AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

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Ageing populations represent both a critical societal challenge and an untapped resource. As Europe and other regions of the world face rising life expectancy and declining birth rates, the question of how best to engage older citizens in social, economic and cultural life becomes increasingly urgent. In rural and mountainous areas such as the Casentino region of Italy, older adults are essential custodians of traditional knowledge and practices that contribute to the sustainability and vitality of their communities. This paper explores the role of active older citizens in building social capital and contributing to community engagement in the Casentino region, with a focus on their ability to generate professionalisation processes that enhance community resilience (Del Gobbo & Federighi, 2021). Social capital, understood as a collective resource based on social relationships and trust (Bourdieu, 1980; Putnam, 1995), is a crucial determinant of a community's ability to adapt to and manage change (Kilpatrick & Abbott-Chapman, 2005). We examine the contributions of older individuals, highlighting the interplay between their life experiences and skills, and the broader social and cultural dynamics of the local area.

active ageing, biography, inland areas, community development, social capital

1. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The concept of social capital has gained considerable traction in the field of community development, particularly in understanding how communities respond to challenges and opportunities. Social capital, as conceptualised by Bourdieu (1980) and Putnam (1995), originates in micro-level interactions between individuals, which must then be embedded within meso- and macro-

level social structures to have an impact. It is through such interactions that trust, reciprocity, and collective identity are built, enabling communities to act collectively in pursuit of shared goals (Del Gobbo, 2024). According to Falk and Kilpatrick (2000), social capital is context-dependent; it depends on the characteristics of a specific community and on how well the human capital within that community is leveraged. The concept of “community efficacy,” as discussed by Kilpatrick and Abbott-Chapman (2005), is closely linked to social capital and refers to a community’s capacity to manage change and influence its own future. This theoretical lens is particularly relevant when examining the role of older citizens in Casentino, where a combination of demographic challenges and rich cultural heritage creates both risks and opportunities for local development. The notion of active ageing further complements this framework by emphasising the agency of older individuals in contributing to societal processes (World Health Organization, 2015). Older adults possess valuable knowledge and skills that can support the social, cultural and economic fabric of their communities. By understanding how these individuals contribute informally to community life, we can begin to recognise the potential for professionalisation processes that translate these informal contributions into more structured and impactful roles (Neyer & Andersson, 2008).

2. THE CASENTINO REGION AND METHODOLOGY

The Casentino is a mountainous rural area in the Tuscan Apennines, renowned for its tangible and intangible cultural heritage. It is an area marked by demographic decline, with an ageing population and limited economic opportunities, yet it also exhibits interesting flows of incoming post-retirement mobility (Regione Toscana, 2022).

Designated as a pilot area within Italy’s National Strategy for Inner Areas (MIUR, 2013), Casentino offers a valuable context for studying the dynamics of community-based regeneration, particularly as they relate to the involvement of older citizens.

The Casentino’s rich cultural landscape includes practices, traditions and local knowledge that have been handed down through the generations. These elements are not only central to the community’s identity, but also represent a potential asset for fostering sustainable development. The REACT project, which aims to regenerate cultural landscapes by enhancing human and social capital, serves as the backdrop for this research, exploring how local resources can be leveraged for community-led development.

In Work Package 2 (WP2), which aims to construct a knowledge framework for the Casentino, the REACT project is studying the territory across four thematic areas:

1. Agro-food and forestry heritage and local craftsmanship
2. Traditions and social practices
3. Landscape and territorial networks
4. Settlements, public spaces and buildings

On the basis of ten thematic focuses, 33 representative case studies from the Casentino were identified and analysed, allowing the researchers to understand both inhabitants and places through field analysis. This led to an interdisciplinary SWOT analysis of all the cases in order to reach a comprehensive understanding and interpretation of the thematic areas. For this particular contribution, three of the 33 case studies were selected for their strong community engagement, all of which originated from participatory community activation processes:

1. **The Casentino Ecomuseum:** The Ecomuseum was created as a participatory project that involves the local population, institutions and associations in managing the cultural heritage of the locality. It is explicitly designed to activate and engage the local community. The Ecomuseum represents an innovative model of heritage valorisation that goes far beyond a mere exhibition space, and is conceived as a dynamic process committed to the continuous research and promotion of intangible heritage and best practices, and the development of sustainable tourism while protecting the land. The Ecomuseum demonstrates valuable opportunities for growth, such as the potential for the further professionalisation of processes and the establishment of a more stable structure. It constitutes the main participatory process from which the other two case studies emerged, showcasing the dynamic and changing nature of community engagement.
2. **The Territorial Educational Pact of Casentino:** Promoted by the Union of Municipalities of Casentino under the scientific direction of the FORLILPSI Department of the University of Florence, this community engagement process began in 2020. The network formed through the Ecomuseum and was tailored to local needs, aligning with regional legislation n.32 of 2002. The pact involves a network of stakeholders, including businesses, public bodies, schools, private entities and the tertiary sector, in order to facilitate inclusive territorial governance. The

use of a pact-like structure has proven to be an effective tool to activate and make visible the social capital expressed by the community.

3. **The Heritage Community:** Heritage communities are organised forms of civil society that foster social networks and human capital relating to intangible heritage, with the aim of encouraging sustainable development (Faro Convention, 2005). The Ecomuseum has collaborated with a number of groups and associations representing heritage communities active in issues related to ritual traditions, the aim being to establish a pact that allows revitalisation and innovation in the transmission of this particular form of local heritage. The organisation of heritage communities is driven by a bottom-up logic; actions taken have no predefined objectives and are strongly desired by the participants. In Casentino, these heritage communities partly emerged from the Ecomuseum network, which is formalising a community engagement process through a pact. This formalisation seeks to give a name to existing informal networks surrounding local traditions, particularly those related to rites of passage.

The three processes described above constitute activators of citizenship and local networks. Interestingly, approximately 90% of the individuals actively involved in these processes are over 50, and more than 60% are retired, in line with local trends. The evidence collected highlights certain contextual factors and conditions that contribute to the definition of professionalisation processes (Federighi, 2021) which can influence the creation of social capital. The REACT research highlighted the role that citizens over 55 can play when they decide to make the skills they have acquired through their experience of life and work available for the development of their community.

The Casentino Ecomuseum guides these community engagement processes and embodies a hybrid professionalism that plays a role in education and care for the local area. The complexity of these community activation processes means they require someone to guide and instigate them, and this allows examination of the professional skills necessary to manage participatory processes that have a significant impact in terms of active citizenship but need to be activated, managed and mediated.

The informal contributions of older adults often mirror professional roles, such as those of cultural mediators, educators, and 'community dynamisers'. However, these hybrid professional figures are typically not acknowledged or formalised, and this limits their potential impact. By identifying and formalising

these roles, it is possible to enhance the contributions of older citizens, ensuring that their skills and knowledge are more effectively utilised for the benefit of the community.

The concept of professionalisation involves the acknowledgement and legitimisation of the informal skills and abilities that individuals acquire through their life experiences (Del Gobbo & Federighi, 2021). In the case of the Casentino, professionalisation processes could help to transform the informal contributions of older citizens into structured roles that are integrated into local development strategies. This could include the creation of new professional figures in the fields of education, cultural heritage management, and community development tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of the locality.

3. CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

While the Casentino benefits from a rich reservoir of social capital, there are also significant challenges that must be addressed in order to fully leverage the potential of older citizens. One of the main challenges is the limited institutional support for community-led initiatives, which often rely on the voluntary efforts of a small number of individuals. This lack of support can hamper the sustainability of such initiatives and limit their ability to generate broader community benefits. Another challenge is the low level of youth participation in community activities, which threatens the continuity of social capital across generations. To address this issue, it is essential to encourage intergenerational collaboration and create opportunities for young people to engage with the community. This could involve the development of educational programmes that focus on local heritage and traditions in an innovative way. The context appears to constitute a laboratory for the observation of professionalisation processes with the potential to define new professional education-related roles in territorial contexts characterised by a high population of over 55s, who are an important local resource. Moreover, the Casentino's cultural heritage is a valuable asset that can be leveraged to attract visitors and generate economic opportunities. By incorporating the contributions of older citizens into local development strategies, it is possible to create a more inclusive and resilient community that values the skills and knowledge of all its members.

CONCLUSION

This paper seeks to highlight the transformative role that older adults play in activating and sustaining social capital within the Casentino community, and in the management and conservation of its cultural landscape. Initiatives such as the Casentino Ecomuseum, the Territorial Educational Pact and the Heritage Communities illustrate how older citizens have the potential to foster networks of trust, facilitate the circulation of local knowledge, and bridge generational gaps. By acknowledging and valuing their contributions, and by addressing the systemic barriers that limit their involvement, it is possible to unlock the potential of ageing populations to drive sustainable rural regeneration. Education plays a crucial role in supporting the active engagement of older citizens and in fostering community development. Lifelong learning opportunities can help older adults to continue developing their skills and to remain active participants in society, helping to combat depopulation and becoming catalysts for social innovation and resilience.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge all the participants in the working group for the competitive study “REACT. Regenerating the cultural landscapes of inland areas in a people-centred perspective” CUP B55F21007810001, funded by Next Generation EU and the Italian National Research Programme (NRP) 2021-2027, for their contribution to the results presented in this paper. We also acknowledge, for their collaboration and the opportunity to share results, researchers engaged on projects co-funded by Next Generation EU as part of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, M4C2 Investment 1.3: •PE_0000015, PE8, Age-It – A new public-private alliance to generate socio-economic, biomedical and technological solutions for an inclusive Italian ageing society. CUP B83C22004800006•PE_0000020, PE5, CHANGES, Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society. CUP: B53C22004010006. The views and opinions expressed in this paper are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the stance of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

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